

Asymptomatic vesical stone randomly discovered in a 78 years old woman admitted for femoral neck fracture. A case report (*Calcul vésical asymptomatique découvert chez une femme de 78 ans reçue pour une fracture sous capitale. Cas clinique*)

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ABSTRACT

Urinary tract stones originate from a variety of conditions, including metabolic and inherited disorders, medical devices, anatomical defects with or without chronic urinary infection. Most cases are idiopathic, in which there is undoubtedly a genetic predisposition, but where environmental and lifestyle factors play an essential role. We report a case of a 78 years old woman who underwent arthroplasty in which an asymptomatic bladder stone was discovered and left untreated purposely.

RESUME

Les calculs urinaires sont de diverses étiologies, notamment des troubles métaboliques et héréditaires, matériel médical, des anomalies anatomiques avec ou sans infection urinaire chronique. La plupart des cas sont idiopathiques, dans lesquels il existe indubitablement une prédisposition génétique, mais où les facteurs environnementaux et de style de vie jouent un rôle important. Nous rapportons le cas d'une femme de 78 ans qui a subi une arthroplastie chez qui un calcul vésical asymptomatique a été découvert et volontairement laissé non traité.

KEYWORDS Asymptomatic vesical stones, vesical stones management, large vesical calculus.

Introduction

Urinary tract stones originate from a variety of conditions, including metabolic and inherited disorders, medical devices, anatomical defects with or without chronic urinary infection. Most cases are idiopathic, in which there is undoubtedly a genetic predisposition, but where environmental and lifestyle factors

play an essential role. We report a case of a 78 years old woman who underwent arthroplasty in which an asymptomatic bladder stone was discovered and left untreated purposely.

Case report

A 78 years old woman with a history of hypertension and ectopic pregnancy, presented at the department of trauma-orthopaedics after a fall occasioned by spontaneous and intense pain. The painful sensation originated from the root of the right pelvic limb. The pain exaggerated when sitting. During the physical examination, we noted lameness of the limb, which was positioned in an external rotation manner. The other parts of the body were without particulars. Imaging (X-ray), (Fig.1,2) revealed a fracture of the femoral neck classified Garden III, and a large calculus (6cm) (Fig.3) in the centre of the bladder. Further

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Figure 1,2: X-ray showing fracture of the right femoral neck and a large calculus in the bladder.

Figure 3: Extracted head of the femur.

Figure 4: Perfectly encapsulated prosthesis, and calculus in the bladder.

investigation: blood count, urea, creatinemia, CRP, blood sugar were all normal.

Hospital course, 6 and 12 months follow-up.

The patient was operated 48 hours after her admission and discharged seven days after the procedure. The procedure consisted of an arthroplasty in which the patient received a 49 size prosthesis. After the operation, we conducted another physical examination to appreciate the motor function of the limb. There was no shortening of the limb, amplitudes on flexion and extension were considered good. A post-surgical X-ray (Fig.4) showed a perfectly encapsulated prosthesis. At her discharge, the patient was able to stand and move with a walker.

Half a year and one year after discharge the patient was examined again to judge her recovery. She still experienced momentary discomfort when walking, but she claimed it did not substantially affect her everyday life and denied any urinary tract issue.

Discussion

Calculus in the bladder usually irritates, leading to a frequent and urgent desire to pass urine, bleeding in the urine (which may be visible or detected only on testing) and recurring attacks of cystitis. Urinary calculi are common; at least one person in 10 will be found to have a urinary calculus at some stage of life. Men are affected three times as commonly as women, so the lifetime risk for a man is at least 15%. Many stones cause no symptoms. Some are found incidentally on x-rays taken for unrelated reasons, so many must be undetected, and the true prevalence will be higher than these figures indicate. Bladder stones are also renowned for their tendency to reoccur, especially in the presence of a urinary catheter. High and uniform fluid intake is the main preventive measure.

Medical controversy

The purpose of the report was to discuss the pertinence and consequences of the medical decision on a common condition. Several authors have discussed the appropriate approach to adopt with bladder stones. Surgical removal, treatment by endoscopic management, shock-wave lithotripsy, medical treatment or no treatment at all, mostly in case of small calculi have been mentioned in the literature. Asymptomatic bladder stones are usually, randomly discovered during routine lab tests. In these cases, the decision to deliver the right treatment depends on many factors. In our context, after explaining all the aspects related to the condition to the patient, she decided to delay her consent for the removal of the calculus arguing that it never caused her any discomfort and feared the physical cost of undergoing two surgical procedures though there was no evident connection between both conditions.

CONCLUSION

Bladder calculi remain one of the central issues of the urinary tract. Their aetiology differs as well as the ways of their management. They may be associated with an extensive range of complications or remain silent until their random discovery. Larger stones tend to cause fewer symptoms, probably due to restricted movement within the bladder. The report results strengthen the fact that large asymptomatic bladder calculi may be ignored in case no discomfort or complication is present. However, the patient should be kept under close watch.

PATIENT CONSENT

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this case report and any accompanying images. A copy of the written consent is available for review by the Editor-in-Chief of this journal.

COMPETING INTERESTS

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

REFERENCES

1. Nerli et al., Asymptomatic Multiple Bladder Stones Treated by Percutaneous Cystolitholapaxy *Med Sur Urol* 2017, 6:2 DOI: 10.4172/2168-9857.1000187
2. Mohamed Omar, Abdullahi Abdulwahab-Ahmed, Hemant Chaparala and Manoj Monga Does Stone Removal Help Patients with Recurrent Urinary Tract Infections? *THE JOURNAL OF UROLOGY* <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.juro.2015.04.096> Vol. 194, 997-1001,
3. De Silva et al. A large bladder stone caused by the intravesical migration of an intrauterine contraceptive device: a case report *Journal of Medical Case Reports* (2017) 11:293 DOI 10.1186/s13256-017-1461-6
4. Eng-Kian Lim, M.D.*, Victor Chia-Hsiang Lin, M.D. Stones Formation Associated with Neobladder Urinary Diversion *Incont Pelvic Floor Dysfunct* 2011; 5(1):25-26
5. Christian Türk et al., EAU Guidelines on Diagnosis and Conservative Management of Urolithiasis <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.eururo.2015.07.040> 0302-2838/2015 European Association of Urology.
6. Bradley F.Schwartz, Marshall L.Stoller The vesical calculi [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0094-0143\(05\)70262-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0094-0143(05)70262-7)
7. Fabio Cesar Miranda Torricelli et al., Surgical management of bladder stones: literature review <http://dx.doi.org/10.1590/S0100-69912013000300011>
8. Ming-Huei Cheng et al., Vesical calculus associated with vesicovaginal fistula <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gmit.2013.07.009>
9. Malladad N, Manjunath DA, Anil R, Radhakrishna V. Clinical study and management of vesical calculus. *Int Surg J* 2018;5:1281-5.
10. Jhanwar P, Parasher V, Khatri R, Gupta V. Giant Vesical Calculus in a Girl Child: Rare Case Report. *MAMC J Med Sci* 2018;4:54
11. Gite VA, Siddiqui AK, Bote SM. Giant vesical calculus in augmented bladder with mitrofanoff procedure. *Arch Int Surg* 2015;5:171-3
12. Ibrahim Nuvit Tahtali, Turgay Karata Giant bladder stone: A case report and review of the literature *Turkish Journal of Urology* 2014; 40(3): 189-91 DOI:10.5152/tud.2014.02603